

STATIC AND MODEL ANALYSIS THROUGH FEA/FEM

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ABSTRACT

The Platform used for goods carrier supports all types of complicated loads coming from the road and pay loads. So, the strength and design of platform play a big role in designing of carrier truck. A platform of 4 wheels, has been studied and analyzed using HYPERMESH software package. Finite element analysis and modal analysis has been done with the help of software to study different loading cases and also vibration modes have been analyzed during the loading condition. Thus, results show stress , displacement and natural frequency of the structure obtained from the platform model.

Keywords: Platform, Hypermesh , Stress analysis , Natural frequency

INTRODUCTION

Now a days increasing demands of platform used for carrier goods vehicle for transportation has been increased not only on cost and weight and also on improved complete vehicle features. This results in increasing focus on optimization and modularization which together with large number of vehicle variants makes it necessary to use efficient analysis methods.

Finite element method/Finite element analysis has become an important part for development of vehicle platform for development of many vehicle features. Platform used for vehicle mounted on chassis body upholds the loads above the platform for various purpose to transport the loads from one place to another.

While it is difficult to quote a date of the invention of the finite element method, the method originated from the need to solve complex elasticity and structural analysis problems in civil and aeronautical engineering. In china, in the later 1950s and early 1960s , based on the computation of dam construction , K.Feng proposed a systematic numerical method for solving partial differential equations. The finite element method obtained its real impetus in the 1960s and 1970s by the developments of J.H. Argyris. A rigorous mathematical basis to the finite element method was provided in 1973 with the publication by Strang and Fix. A variety of specializations under the umbrella of the mechanical engineering discipline (such as aeronautical, biomechanical, and automotive industries) commonly use integrated FEM in design and development of their products.

In present work finite element model has been built up for 4 wheel goods carrier platform in order to simulate the effect of different loads under different conditions. A static analysis with necessary boundary and loading condition have been applied on the model using HYPERMESH software and to evaluate the induced stresses and deformations on the platform during the different loading conditions. Also modal analysis has been done on platform to obtained natural frequency of the system.

Thus the results obtained from analysis on the platform is used to design the platform more accurately and precisely and helpful to finalize the design without any destructive method. It was found that the results obtained from Hypermesh software is almost near the experimental values.

Finite element analysis of platform

For the FE Analysis, it is necessary to create a solid model of platform in order to create a FE model. In present work, load is distributed to all platform uniformly under gravity loading. Loads are applied at their position under loading boundary condition to study the impact of loading in form of stress, displacement and frequency.

Mount aggregates Details :

S. No.	Mass (Kg)
Shelter with equipments	3487
DG Set	800
Fuel Tank	800
Load Bank	200
<i>Shelter Base Platform (FE Model)</i>	<i>1864</i>
Total	7151

Model of Platform

The platform used in the form of step , parasolid in hypermesh software to obtained the hypermesh file. The model has 6058mm length and 2438mm wide. The material of platform is steel(IS 2062:FE 410) with yield strength 250MPa and tensile strength of 410MPa. The properties of platform are listed in below table.

Table: Properties of Platform material

Modulus of Elasticity E(Pa)	210x10 ⁹
Density(kg/m ³)	7800
Poisson ratio	0.3
Yield strength(MPa)	250
Ultimate tensile strength(MPa)	410

In elasto-static problem, each element forms a stiffness matrix, [K], relating forces [F] and displacements[u] at nodes. The size of the stiffness matrix is equal to the number of nodes per element multiplies by the number of freedom per nodes, as in the following

$$[F] = [K] [U]$$

In eigenvalue problem, the characteristic matrix is formed as

$$\{[K] - \omega^2 [M]\} [U] = 0$$

Where M is the mass matrix, ω^2 are eigenvalues, and u is the eigenvectors. In structural dynamics, the values are the natural frequencies and the vectors are mode shapes.

Loads and Boundary Conditions :

1. Platform's mass is inclusive of all equipment.

2. Platform with the mounted aggregates lifted from side slots of the four ISO corners.
3. All the degrees of freedom at the four corners restrained.
4. 2.3g vertically downward acceleration is applied.

The meshed platform model is shown below figure 1.

Figure 1: Meshing or Discretization of Platform model

Stress and Displacement developed after applying loads shown in figure 2 and 3 below.

Contour Plot
Element Stresses (2D & 3D)(vonMises, Max)
Global System
Advanced Average

300.00
150.00
131.25
112.50
93.75
75.00
56.25
37.50
18.75
0.00
No result

Figure 2: Von Mises stress for most of the structure is below 100 MPa

Figure 3: Maximum Displacement of 3.69 mm at the middle portion of the platform.

Modal Analysis :

In this analysis different frequency modes has been obtained under loading Condition.

Figures 4 , 5 ,6 shown below are modal analysis for the platform.

Figure 4: First Bending mode experienced by platform at 16.65 Hz.

Image magnified by 500 times

Figure 5: Second Bending mode experienced by platform at 35.8 Hz.
Image magnified by 500 times

Figure 6: First twisting mode experienced by platform at 39.36 Hz.
Image magnified by 1000 times

Results and discussion :

The above results shown from figure 2 to 6 of stress , displacement and modal analysis of platform after analysis. It can be seen that maximum Von Mises stress developed is 100MPa and displacement is 3.69mm. The first mode of frequency is about 16.95Hz and second mode of frequency is 35.8Hz in bending whereas in twisting it is 39.36Hz.

Conclusion:

We find that the stress and displacement obtained is under safe condition of platform used. So, the structure for loading about 7 Ton is safe to use. Rest of safety depends on manufacturer used for it. Otherwise results obtained for the platform is good enough for the manufacturer to used these values accordingly.

Future Scope :

1. To decrease the manufacturing cost by the use of FEM/FEA.
2. Analysis method is the non-destructive method for the design of structure over another method so can be used widely by the designer.

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